

Highlights

Towards Secure and Scalable VANET Infrastructures using ACME and TPM-Enabled Device Attestation

- Automatic device certificate issuance with ACME and TPM
- Evaluation by measuring both time and communication overhead
- Demonstrated the applicability for enhancing security in VANETs

Towards Secure and Scalable VANET Infrastructures using ACME and TPM-Enabled Device Attestation

Abstract

As the number of edge devices continues to grow exponentially, ensuring their security and trustworthiness has become increasingly critical. In edge computing environments, the deployment of heterogeneous devices across distributed and often untrusted locations poses significant challenges for secure software maintenance, identity verification, and compliance with cybersecurity standards. These challenges introduce vulnerabilities that can be exploited by attackers to compromise sensitive data or disrupt system operations. To address this concern, this work presents an automated mechanism based on the Automatic Certificate Management Environment (ACME) protocol and its device attestation extension for provisioning cryptographic certificates to devices equipped with a Trusted Platform Module (TPM). In particular, we propose a Public Key Infrastructure (PKI) framework that enables secure communication by verifying device identity and ensuring the confidentiality, integrity, and authenticity of exchanged data. Our approach provides strong assurance that devices are operating in a trusted state, with cryptographic keys securely stored and bound to measured system integrity. We validate the solution through a practical implementation and demonstrate its effectiveness in Vehicular Ad Hoc Networks (VANETs), where vehicles can automatically obtain ephemeral certificates to establish trusted, privacy-preserving communication. This capability not only strengthens security in connected and autonomous vehicles but also lays the groundwork for scalable, standards-compliant security infrastructures in connected transportation systems.

Keywords: ACME, Device Attestation, Trusted Platform Module, Cybersecurity, Edge computing, Certificate Management

1. Introduction

With the rapid advancement of Internet of Things (IoT), the number of smart and connected devices is increasing exponential. These IoT devices, which generally gather data, can cause problems in traditional cloud computing: the large scale of data can cause a bandwidth bottleneck, slow response, and can compromise security and privacy if not handled properly. In this context, Edge computing has emerged as a new computing paradigm where processing is performed on devices at the network's edge. Being closer to users and the source of data, response times are improved, while bottlenecks are reduced [1]. Edge computing is starting to be implemented in applications that require low latency, high volumes of data, and device mobility. This includes systems for health monitoring, smart grid, cloud gaming, content delivery and autonomous vehicles [2, 3, 4]. One of the main concerns with Edge computing is the privacy and security of user's data, which has led to the definition of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) as a framework to unify data security and privacy guarantees across EU countries [5, 6]. It is important to note that edge devices are more susceptible to cyber-physical attacks when compared to traditional cloud-based systems, as they generally have weaker computational power and more fragile defense systems, while being delocalized and closer to users. Therefore, evaluating the working status of the device and assessing if it has been compromised become a more complex task. Moreover, Edge computing is based on the use of different devices with different operating systems and communication protocols that might receive support, or not, from the manufacturer or maintainer, thus making harder the design and standardization of the security measures [7].

Many approaches have been proposed to address these security and privacy concerns, ranging from traditional cryptographic encryption and authentication schemes for secure data exchange, to more recent Artificial Intelligence (AI), Machine Learning (ML), and blockchain-based methods for detecting anomalous behavior among network nodes [8]. However, these solutions often suffer from limited scalability, high computational overhead, and complex deployment requirements, making them difficult to apply in dynamic, resource-constrained edge environments such as Vehicular Ad Hoc Networks (VANETs). To overcome these limitations, this work explores the use of the Automatic Certificate Management Environment (ACME) protocol, developed by the Internet Security Research Group (ISRG), as an

automation layer that makes Public Key Infrastructure (PKI) more scalable and practical for modern distributed systems [9]. Unlike conventional PKI setups that require manual certificate provisioning and renewal, ACME enables automated, secure, and continuous certificate life cycle management. This approach not only ensures device authentication but also reduces operational overhead, enhances responsiveness, and supports dynamic, multi-tenant deployments, making it particularly well-suited for high-mobility environments like VANETs [10]. Note that the certificates generated can be further used to establish secure communication channels with other elements, as well as to encrypt or sign any relevant information, among other uses. Because of that, our study also relies on trusted platform modules (TPM) to address and complete the challenge from the ACME Certificate Authority (CA) in order to enhance security and privacy. Moreover, in VANETs there is a constant exchange of messages between participants to inform about road, weather or emergency conditions. Since these messages need to be authenticated and their integrity guaranteed for the vehicles to trust the network, the proposed solution provides an ideal fit, as it would provide implicit proof that the node transmitting the information has been authenticated and its software and hardware has not been tampered with. Overall, we demonstrate that ACME brings scalability, automation, and enhanced trust to VANETs enabling secure vehicle-to-vehicle (V2V) and vehicle-to-infrastructure (V2I) communications [11].

In particular, the manuscript is structured as follows. After this introduction, Section II presents a literature review covering the ACME protocol and other existing alternatives for certificate provisioning, along with a description of VANETs. Section III details the design and implementation of the proposed solution, including a step-by-step explanation of the certificate issuance process. Section IV illustrates the potential of combining ACME with the TPM in VANETs, demonstrating how this integration can enable smart vehicles to securely and privately exchange critical information. Section V concludes the manuscript by summarizing the main findings and outlining future research directions.

2. Literature Review

A PKI is based on the use of digital certificates and public key cryptography in order to bind a public key to an identity. This binding is performed by the registration and issuance of a certificate by a so called CA. While this

process of issuance can be performed manually, it does not escalate properly, specially for the high volume of devices expected in edge computing. Because of that, different automated processes have emerged to automatically grant certificate to devices, generally after they prove their identity or successfully pass a challenge [12]. Examples of these automated protocols include the Simple Certificate Enrollment Protocol (SCEP) [13], Enrollment over Secure Transport (EST) [14], and more recently, ACME.

In the case of SCEP, it uses cryptographic message syntax to construct the messages to perform the necessary PKI operations over HTTP. The main objective of the protocol is to be simple, so all PKI operations can be performed in just two transfer back and forth between the client and the CA. However, the simple verifications implemented in SCEP make necessary the use of improved authentication methods to protect the certificate generation process [15] [16].

Regarding EST, it uses Certificate Management over Cryptographic Message Syntax (CMS) messages, transmitting the data using HTTP with TLS. This introduces an authenticated and authorized channel of communication between the CA and the client for the requests and responses. It also allows for the establishment of extensions in order to add new functionalities [17]. EST is optimized for traditional provisioning workflows, where the certificate validity is long, so it does not provide sophisticated renewal automation.

Lastly, ACME has brought the possibility of automatizing interactions between clients and CAs, such that a PKI can be established with minimal intervention and reduced cost [18]. The automatized verification for granting the certificate is performed by a series of different ad-hoc mechanisms, called challenges, depending on the particular use. This way, the ACME CA can be extended for any particular use. For instance, in web servers applications, the HTTP challenge is usually used (referred to as "http-01"), where the client proves the control over a web domain name by provisioning some HTTP resources in order to comply with the challenge [10].

In this case, the focus is on the Device Attestation (referred to as *device-attest-01*) challenge for the ACME protocol. This challenge relies on the use of a TPM, or another compatible Hardware Security Module (HSM), to automatically provide certificates in a privacy preserving manner to the edge devices [19]. A TPM is a security component standardized by the Trusted Computing Group (TCG) that provides a unique device identity in the form of a certificate provisioned during manufacturing. It also offers attestation capabilities to edge nodes, allowing a third party to verify the device's in-

egrity and assess whether it is a trustworthy peer [20, 21]. Consequently, the edge node can respond to a challenge by supplying the required attestation data from the TPM, thereby enabling the automatic issuance of certificates without human intervention. Therefore, compared to other solutions, ACME with the Device Attestation offers the advantages of a secure, modern, and extensible standard. It enables fully automated certificate management with no human intervention required beyond the initial enrollment and setup. And, most importantly, it incorporates device attestation data, which strengthens trust and infrastructure security by preventing access from malicious or tampered nodes. All of these advantages make ACME an emerging and promising use case for implementing secure communications within VANETs.

VANETs are dynamic mobile networks in which vehicles are registered through dedicated authorities known as Roadside Units (RSUs), while each vehicle is equipped with an On-Board Unit (OBU). Vehicles move freely on the road and communicate either with another vehicle (V2V) or with RSUs (V2I) using short-range wireless technologies. These vehicles often have GPS capabilities and a variety of sensors that allow them to share information about road conditions or accidents with nearby vehicles. This leads to improved user experiences, such as automatic rerouting to avoid traffic congestion or receiving alerts about accidents or adverse weather conditions along the current route. Given the safety-critical nature of these communications, it is essential to ensure the authenticity and trustworthiness of exchanged messages to prevent accidents or the spread of malicious information by attackers [22].

To provide the required authentication and privacy in VANETs, identity-based authentication schemes have been explored in the literature. These approaches aim to balance the conflicting goals of preserving user privacy, so that vehicles cannot be tracked, and ensuring traceability, so malicious actors can be identified and removed from the network. Some key challenges for the deployment of VANETs with identity based authentication include [11]:

1. Need for efficient Key Management: managing and disseminating cryptographic keys in VANET is a challenge due to the dynamism of the network, with frequent entering and exiting of the vehicles. Therefore, a robust, scalable and fast key management strategy is needed.
2. Revocation challenges: revoking the certificates of malicious vehicles is critical to maintain trust in both the participants and the exchanged

information. In this case, traditional methods like the use of Certificate Revocation Lists (CRLs) may present too much latency or overhead.

3. Interoperability: different manufacturers must collaborate to achieve a common standard for the authentication of the vehicles.
4. Integration with existing infrastructure: legacy systems that do not support the identity based authentication would need to be integrated and incorporated, with the corresponding complexity.

Based on these challenges, the ACME device-attest specification emerges as a promising solution for providing On-Board Units (OBUs) with certificates through identity-based authentication. ACME offers a scalable, automated, and efficient protocol for certificate issuance, supported by multiple implementations and broad adoption, effectively addressing many of the challenges previously described [23]. Moreover, integrating device attestation within ACME enhances trust by ensuring that messages and alerts originate from verified, legitimate sources, as further demonstrated in Section IV. The design and implementation of our proposed ACME-based framework is detailed in next section, describing its main components and the communication flow used to automatically provision certificates to edge nodes.

3. Design and implementation

This section includes a description of the design and technical implementation of the proposed solution. First, the framework of the different elements and their roles are explained, followed by a detailed description of the process for the certificate to be granted.

3.1. Framework

The proposed ACME device-attest framework is composed of four main components, as shown in Fig. 1, which collectively enable automated, hardware-based certificate provisioning through remote attestation. Each component plays a distinct role in ensuring the authenticity and integrity of the participating edge devices.

1. **ACME device-attest Client (Client):** The client runs on the edge device (e.g., an OBU) and is responsible for fulfilling the ACME device-attest challenge. To meet this challenge, the client must generate an Attestation Object according to the ACME specification, encapsulating cryptographically signed evidence of the device's identity and integrity.

Figure 1: Communication diagram for the ACME device-attest process

This process relies on TPM, using its Endorsement Key (EK), a unique key burned into the TPM during manufacturing, and the Attestation Key (AK), which is generated later by the TPM and used to sign attestation data. The client also includes integrity measurements automatically gathered by the Integrity Measurement Architecture (IMA), a part of the Linux security subsystem, which automatically collects hashes of critical files and configurations [24]. These measurements demonstrate that the device is operating in a trusted state. By combining TPM-backed keys with IMA integrity data, the client can automatically prove its authenticity and integrity to the Attestation Server, allowing the certificate issuance process to proceed without human intervention.

2. **Attestation CA Server (At-S):** This server handles credential activation and issues the challenge to verify the client's identity. It also validates all necessary data before issuing the signed AK certificate required by the ACME challenge. The Attestation CA may run as a service alongside the ACME CA Server on the same device or be implemented on a separate device/server. This server has access to the databases needed to store and retrieve relevant information during the attestation process.
3. **ACME CA Server (AC-S):** The ACME CA Server implements the ACME protocol to handle certificate life cycle management. It receives requests from clients, issues and verifies challenges, and, once the attestation phase is successfully completed, processes the Certificate Signing Request (CSR) submitted by the client. Upon successful validation, the ACME CA issues a signed certificate, enabling secure, authenticated communication among trusted devices. This automated approach elim-

inates manual provisioning, reduces operational overhead, and improves scalability across large, distributed networks.

4. **Databases (DBs):** Two databases support the attestation framework. One of them stores information about the attempts of devices to pass the challenge, enabling verification and logging that the attestation is recent and whether the client was properly authenticated. Another database maintains the Integrity Measurement Architecture (IMA) logs, which are checked at the start of the challenge to verify the device's integrity. The information stored in the databases is illustrated in Fig. 2. On the one hand, the session data includes:
 - (a) **AttData:** Platform Configuration Register (PCR) values from the TPM, reflecting the current integrity state of the device. In this implementation, AttData includes the "boot aggregate" hash recorded by IMA, which allows detecting unauthorized modifications in the software stack of the edge node.
 - (b) **Transaction ID:** A unique nonce used to ensure that each attestation session is distinct, preventing replay attacks.
 - (c) **Time Request:** A UNIX timestamp marking the initiation of the client's attestation request, useful for timeout validation and audit logging.
 - (d) **Unique ID:** A hardware-bound identifier derived from the SHA-256 hash of the TPM's EK public key and encoded in Base64, ensuring a consistent and verifiable device identity.

On the other hand, the provisioned attestation DB stores the association between each device's Unique ID and its corresponding valid attestation data (AttData) values. These values are initially registered by the maintainer of the edge node during the setup phase and are later retrieved during the attestation challenge. If the IMA values change due to, e.g., software modifications or new library installations, the maintainer can reinitialize the reference values in the database to preserve system trustworthiness. The maintainer might also decide not to measure certain components that change with high frequency to avoid frequent re-initialization.

3.2. ACME device-attest workflow

This section describes the process that is followed by the Edge Node to obtain a certificate. The overall scheme of the ACME device-attest challenge is illustrated in Fig. 3. Note that the diagram does not include the

Figure 2: Data organization in the corresponding databases

initialization step, as it is assumed to be completed prior to the start of the workflow.

0. **Initialization:** Both the Edge Node and the CAs must be pre-provisioned with the necessary components. The Edge Node receives the CA's chain certificates to establish trusted TLS connections, while the CAs are configured with two databases: one linking each Edge Node's unique identifier to its valid integrity states (SHA-256 hashes), and another used to log session data such as transaction IDs, attestation records, and timestamps for traceability and debugging.
1. **ACME Account Registration:** The attestation workflow begins with the ACME client registering an account with the ACME CA. This step follows the same principles as other ACME challenges (e.g., HTTP-01 or DNS-01), establishing the foundational trust relationship between the client and the CA. The client first generates an asymmetric key pair and uses its private key to sign the registration request, thereby proving control over the key material. In this implementation, the registration process is simplified to focus on automated device enrollment, omitting Terms of Service (TOS) agreements or user-provided metadata that are typically required in web-based ACME deployments. Upon successful verification, the CA creates a new account for the client and returns an acknowledgment confirming the registration. Once the account is active, all ACME-based certificate issuance processes follow a common sequence consisting of four main stages [10]:
 - (a) Order submission.

- (b) Challenge response: The client demonstrates control over the requested identifier. In this case, the proof is based on the device-attest challenge, where TPM-based attestation replaces conventional domain or HTTP validation methods.
 - (c) Order finalization: After a successful challenge, the client sends a CSR containing the desired public key and identifier.
 - (d) Certificate issuance.
2. **Order Certificate:** After successfully registering an account, the ACME client requests a certificate from the CA, which responds with a "device-attest-01" challenge. In this step, the Edge Node must prove control over its Permanent Identifier by embedding this information within the attestation statement included in the challenge response [25]. The ACME CA in this implementation is configured to handle only device-attest-01 challenges. The format of the challenge that the ACME CA sends is shown in Fig. 4, which includes: (a) a *type* field, set to "device-attest-01"; (b) a *URL* indicating the endpoint where the response must be sent; (c) a *status* field, reflecting the current state of the challenge (pending, valid, invalid, expired, or revoked); and (d) a unique *token*, a random 128-bit base64url-encoded value used by the Edge Node to construct its response.

```
{
  "type": "device-attest-01",
  "url": "https://url.com/acme/chall/UDJ5tvY5N6k",
  "status": "pending",
  "token": "9gzxxDj9XPiPCAGumMyMyAXP0RsoM3ismGiRyewFeYI"
}
```

Figure 4: Format of the challenge sent by the ACME CA

3. **Attestation Statement Generation:** Once the ACME CA issues the device-attest-01 challenge, the Edge Node generates the Attestation Statement to prove possession of the Permanent Identifier. The process begins with the creation of a Key Authorization, formed by concatenating the challenge token received from the ACME CA with the client's ACME account public key, as described in the protocol specification [10] and shown in Fig. 5. The JSON Web Key (JWK) Thumbprint is obtained as indicated in its specification [26].

Figure 3: ACME device-attest implementation

```
keyAuthorization = token || . || base64url(Thumbprint(accountKey))
```

Figure 5: KeyAuthorization building

Then, this Key Authorization serves as the challenge input for generating a WebAuthn-based Attestation Object (AttObj) [19], whose format is detailed in Fig. 6.

```
attObj = {  
  authData: bytes,  
  attStmtType  
}  
  
attStmtTemplate = (  
  fmt: text,  
  attStmt: { * tstr => any };  
)
```

Figure 6: Attestation Object Format

This format is designed to support multiple attestation types for different HSMS, such as YubiKey or Apple’s Secure Enclave. In this case, the focus is on the specific structure used for devices that include a TPM, which can be seen in Fig. 7. Therefore, the resulting AttObj encodes essential evidence regarding the TPM and its cryptographic state, including:

```

attStmtType = (
    fmt: "tpm",
    attStmt: tpmStmtFormat
)

tpmStmtFormat = {
    ver: "2.0",
    (
        alg: COSEAlgorithmIdentifier,
        x5c: [ aikCert: bytes, *(caCert: bytes) ]
    )
    sig: bytes,
    certInfo: bytes,
    pubArea: bytes
}

```

Figure 7: TPM Attestation Object format

- (a) *"fmt"*: type of attestation statement, TPM in this case.
- (b) *"ver"*: TPM version, set to the latest specification (2.0).
- (c) *"alg"*: signing algorithm. In this case, ECDSA using P-256.
- (d) *"aik, caCert"*: AK Certificate in X.509 format, plus the certificate chain used to sign it. This AK certificate contains the Permanent Identifier among other data to verify whether the challenge was answered successfully. This certificate must be signed by a CA trusted by the ACME CA, which in this implementation is the Attestation CA.
- (e) *"sig"*: cryptographic proof of the TPM's properties and the credentials, signed by the attestation private key. It is designated in Section 11.3.4 of the TCG specification as *TPMT_SIGNATURE* [27].
- (f) *"certInfo"*: information regarding the TPM and attestation metadata. It is designated in Section 10.12.8 of the TCG specification as *TPMS_ATTEST* [27].
- (g) *"pubArea"*: TPM public key, as also established in Section 12.2.4 of [27].

The Edge Node signs the hashed Key Authorization (called *"attToBeSigned"*) with its attestation private key, producing the signature stored in *"sig"*. The complete Attestation Object (Fig. 8), is then sent to the ACME CA as the challenge response.

```

POST /acme/chall/UDJ5tvY5N6k
Host: url.com
Content-Type: application/jose+json

{
  "protected" : base64url({
    "alg" : "ES256",
    "kid" : "https://url.com/acme/acct/evOfKhNU60wg",
    "nonce" : "SS2sSl1PtspvFZ08kNtzKd",
    "url" : https://example.com/acme/chall/UDJ5tvY5N6k
  }),
  "payload" : base64url({
    "attObj" : base64url(WebAuthn attestation object),
  }),
  "signature" : "Q1bURgJoEslbD1c5...3pYdSMLio57mQNN4"
}

```

Figure 8: Contents of the JSON sent to the CA to answer the challenge

In standard ACME device-attest flows, this challenge only confirms control of the Permanent Identifier, not the platform’s identity and integrity. Therefore, any TPM-equipped device could theoretically obtain a valid certificate by answering the challenge. To mitigate this limitation, the proposed framework introduces an Attestation CA that first validates the device’s identity and integrity before signing the AK certificate (aikCert). Only pre-authorized devices verified by the Attestation CA can successfully complete the ACME challenge, ensuring that certificates are issued exclusively to authenticated and trusted Edge Nodes. The steps followed for this particular process are:

4. **Verifying Edge Node identity:** Before attesting the device’s integrity, the Attestation CA first validates the identity of the Edge Node through a TPM-based credential activation challenge. As illustrated in Fig. 3 (steps 4.1–4.6), verification begins by loading the TPM manufacturer-provisioned EK, typically a 2048-bit RSA key. From this EK, the node generates an Attestation Key (AK), which serves as a subordinate identity key. The associated information is sent to the Attestation CA (step 4.1).

Upon receiving this data, the CA verifies the validity of the EK certificate to ensure it originates from a trusted manufacturer (step 4.2). If valid, the CA generates a credential blob that contains a random secret encrypted with the AK public key (step 4.3). This blob is returned to

the Edge Node, which must decrypt it using its TPM's private AK and send the recovered secret back to the Attestation CA (steps 4.4–4.5). Successful decryption in step 4.6 confirms exclusive control over the AK and, therefore, authenticates the device's identity.

If the verification fails, the process is halted. By maintaining a whitelist of trusted EK certificate authorities, the architecture ensures that only approved TPM-equipped devices can participate in the system.

- 5. Integrity verification:** The integrity verification process relies on the Linux kernel's IMA module, which records cryptographic measurements of the system's state during boot. When enabled, IMA computes hashes of critical components, such as system libraries and files accessible by the root user, and extends them into the TPM's PCRs. These registers store values cumulatively by hashing new data with the existing register content. By default, IMA extends its measurements into PCR 10, which reflects the overall integrity of the system. An example of IMA output, showing the hash of a file's contents and the corresponding PCR extension, is presented in Fig. 9 and corresponds to step 5.1 in Fig. 3.

PCR	template-hash	filedata-hash	filename-hint
10	9e1f34... ima-ng	sha256: 1801e1...	boot_aggregate
10	8b1683... ima-ng	sha256: efdd24...	/init
10	ed893b... ima-ng	sha256: 1fd312...	/usr/lib64/ld-2.14.so
10	9051e8... ima-ng	sha256: 3d3553...	/etc/ld.so.cache

Figure 9: IMA values obtained during the boot process

Once the device's identity has been confirmed (step 4.6 in Fig. 3), the Attestation CA initiates integrity attestation by sending a nonce to the client (step 5.2) to prevent replay attacks and ensure freshness. The Edge Node responds with a TPM Quote and a signature (steps 5.3 and 5.4). The TPM Quote includes a signed selection of PCR values, their composite hash, and the nonce provided by the Attestation CA, representing the current integrity state of the device.

The Attestation CA verifies that the received quote was signed using the valid AK and that the nonce matches the one previously sent (step 5.5). If the signature or nonce verification fails, the attestation is re-

jected, indicating that the data is either stale or not generated by a genuine TPM.

Finally, the attestation data is compared against the pre-provisioned reference values stored in the database. Each Edge Node is uniquely identified, allowing the CA to query its known-good PCR values corresponding to a valid integrity state. If the received PCR values do not match any registered state, the device's integrity cannot be confirmed (either due to tampering or unrecorded software updates) and the attestation process is halted.

6. **Signature of aikCert:** Before responding to the ACME CA's "device-attest-01" challenge, the client must obtain a valid signature for its AK Certificate from the Attestation CA. To achieve this, the client sends the newly generated but unsigned AK Certificate to the Attestation CA, which verifies the request, signs the certificate, and includes it within the Attestation Statement. To ensure confidentiality and integrity during this exchange, all transmitted data is encrypted using AES-GCM (Galois/Counter Mode) with a 32-byte secret key that was securely established during the identity verification phase. This secret key is generated by the Attestation CA and delivered to the client encrypted with the AK, ensuring that only the client and the CA can decrypt the communication. The use of AES-GCM not only guarantees confidentiality but also provides built-in integrity verification, meaning that any alteration of the cyphertext such as a man-in-the-middle attack would result in decryption failure, immediately halting the process [28]. Furthermore, all communication between the client and both CAs is transmitted over HTTPS (HTTP over TLS) to provide an additional security layer. Upon receiving the encrypted AK Certificate, the Attestation CA decrypts it, applies its signature, re-encrypts the signed certificate, and returns it to the client. The client then decrypts the response and embeds the signed AK Certificate into the Attestation Statement, which is subsequently used to complete the ACME "device-attest-01" challenge.
7. **Attestation Statement validation:** On the server side, the ACME CA must validate all the information received from the Edge Node within the Attestation Statement. To initiate the process, the ACME CA reconstructs and stores the key authorization (referred to as "*att-ToBeSigned*") using the token provided during the challenge, in combination with the ACME client account key, following the same pro-

cedure performed by the client. The validation process then proceeds according to the steps defined in Section 8 of [29]:

- (a) Verify "*attStmt*": The CA first ensures that the *attStmt* is a properly formatted CBOR-encoded structure that can be successfully decoded. If the data is malformed or cannot be decoded, the validation process is immediately aborted.
- (b) Verify "*certInfo*": This step constitutes the core of the validation process. The CA inspects the fields of the *certInfo* structure to confirm that all expected values are present and correct. Specifically, it checks whether the *magic* field is equal to *TPM_GENERATED_VALUE*, the *type* field corresponds to *TPM_ATTEST_CERTIFY*, and that the *extraData* field contains the hash of *attToBeSigned* computed using the indicated *alg* value. Furthermore, the *sig* field must represent a valid signature over *certInfo*, verifiable using the attestation public key included in the *AKCert*. Successful verification of this signature confirms that the Edge Node controls the permanent identifier, as this identifier is embedded in the Subject Alternative Name (SAN) field of the *AKCert*.
- (c) Verify "*KeyAuthorization*": Finally, the CA verifies that the key authorization conveyed by the *attToBeSigned* value matches the one it previously generated and stored when issuing the challenge. This step uses the *sig* data included in the client's challenge response to confirm authenticity and prevent replay or substitution attacks.

8. **Generate and sign certificate:** Once the ACME client successfully passes the device-attestation challenge, the Edge Node proceeds to submit its CSR to the CA. The CA validates the request, signs it, and returns the resulting certificate to the client. This certificate is subsequently recognized as valid across all components that trust the ACME CA from which it originates. Moreover, the certificate's attributes can be tailored to suit the specific functional or security requirements of its role within the architecture.

An essential aspect of PKI management is maintaining certificate validity through renewal and ensuring trust through revocation. Renewal enables a device or user to obtain a new valid certificate when the current one expires or is about to. The Device Attestation challenge does not define a distinct

renewal process, so it is expected to reuse the same certificate issuance flow by submitting a new order, where some previously provided information can be reused or omitted. Revocation, on the other hand, allows the exclusion of compromised or misbehaving entities. It can be implemented in two ways:

- Passive revocation, where the CA simply stops issuing new certificates but allows existing ones to remain valid until expiration. This method is typically used with short-lived certificates (e.g., 24 hours).
- Active revocation, which provides real-time invalidation of certificates through mechanisms such as CRLs [30], or the Online Certificate Status Protocol (OCSP) [31]. Therefore, although this approach adds operational complexity, the real-time removal of misbehaving devices is particularly interesting for vehicular transportation systems. In these environments, where safety and trust must be maintained continuously, active revocation mechanisms are preferable to ensure that compromised or unauthorized vehicles are immediately excluded from the network.

3.3. ACME device-attest implementation

The ACME device-attest workflow was implemented and validated using two Raspberry Pi 5 (8 GB) boards: one as the Client and the other as the Verifier, hosting both the ACME CA and Attestation CA. The Client employed an Infineon OPTIGA™ SLB9672 TPM as its Secure Element (Fig. 10). This implementation is based on three components:

- ACME CA: based on the Smallstep Step CA [32], a CA that has current support for the server side of the ACME Device Attestation challenge, among others.
- Attestation CA: built using the Go-Attestation library [33] and aligned with the Remote ATtestation procedureS (RATS) Architecture [20] to provide device identity and integrity verification.
- Client, adapted from an open-source ACME device-attest client [34], modified to interface with a physical TPM and support the Attestation CA challenge through Go-Attestation.

The message flow during the process is shown in Fig. 11, which has been annotated to represent the steps outlined in Fig. 3. It can be seen that after CA initialization, the Edge Node's attestation data is registered in the

Figure 10: Test bed used for the ACME device attest challenge

Client	Attestation CA	ACME CA
<pre> Certificate has expired. Time to renovate it Registering ACME account... Creating ACME order... Retrieving the challenge from the response... Started generating payload... There is 1 EKs in TPM 2.0 chip Version of TPM 2.0 chip : 2 Interface of TPM 2.0 chip : 1 Vendor info of TPM 2.0 chip : SLB9672 Vendor Name of TPM 2.0 chip : Infineon Firmware version of TPM 2.0 chip : 16.13 Sending the attestation parameters to server... Receiving encrypted credentials from server... Starting attestation... Done generating payload! Fulfilling the ACME challenge... Fulfilling the ACME challenge... Success fulfilling the ACME challenge Creating a CSR... Finalizing the ACME order... Success obtaining a certificate using ACME device-attest -----BEGIN CERTIFICATE----- MIICITCAI6gAwIBAgIRAMVke/gKH10JyZkz89BwCgYIKoZIzj0 eHk4QjEwM6GCSqGSIb3DQEBAQUAA4IBDwAwAQEAggEKA0I BAQDQg0117kN6N8Fz06IapRud0wP 74LAVWEG F4Zy9egK/Vh1sIR0uUayZNIrcFeg+1LSr/QqR9MOK4uP PER09JX In+AbK7V Zr69LxkF3L0x2eYNShbz6zpw98TK7sy0a6ZdrnoT9M60 p0qZaJj sBTEmy1z </pre>	<pre> Serving on port: :8080Certificate verified: true Database opened and pinged successfully Edge Node is already registered Passed Activation Parameter Created the challenge correctly, sending it... Secrets match, client with ID 321151 passed the challenge Generating nonce for client with ID:321151... The quote was checked successfully! Database opened and pinged successfully Edge Node integrity was successfully verified Database opened and pinged successfully Data inserted in DB Client with ID:321151 was registered successfully! Session ID: Victorville-hoariness's-diacritic's-dx0g5te67554eXed7h3kQv9a2u MlEPr-vwK96004u </pre>	<pre> INFO[0039] duration=324.619µs do ration-n=324819 fields.time="2025-02-07T12:50:20+01:00" method=GET nameca_path =/acme/directory protocol=HTTP/2.0 referer=remote-address=":" request_id =44330786 acsh=4090-4844-20134601c921 response={"newNonce":"","https://localhos t:443/acme/acme/new-nonce","newAccount":"","https://localhost:443/acme/acme/new -account","newOrder":"","https://localhost:443/acme/acme/new-order","revokeCer rt":"","https://localhost:443/acme/acme/revoke-cert","keyChange":"","https://lo calhost:443/acme/acme/key-change":""} size=287 status=200 user-agent=golang.org/x /crypto/acme user-id= INFO[0039] duration=50.158748ms du ration-n=50158748 fields.time="2025-02-07T12:50:20+01:00" method=HEAD nameca_n once=QCZTL1G0NMF1ECPNMW6d60p131FAUficc0S80V path=/acme/acme/new-nonce proto col=HTTP/2.0 referer=remote-address=":" request-id=228a5332-9ac7-474b-a359-8e 57e5c09011 size=0 status=200 user-agent=golang.org/x/crypto/acme user-id= INFO[0039] duration=25.33878ms dur ation-n=25338780 fields.time="2025-02-07T12:50:20+01:00" method=POST nameca_n once=cl130R093SEdppF87XZqPjUT0FAFTFZ2V420Q path=/acme/acme/new-account prot ocol=HTTP/2.0 referer=remote-address=":" request-id=0a102cd9-3234-4317-1194-4 5855a1906b0 response={"status":"","valid":"","orders":"","https://localhost:443/a cme/acme/account/frkZL63a6b0b6e10f76bc31f9j058M/orders":""} size=110 status=200 user-agent=golang.org/x/crypto/acme user-id= INFO[0039] duration=58.237966ms du ration-n=58237966 fields.time="2025-02-07T12:50:20+01:00" method=POST nameca_n once=MOBKXMSUUYV042QVhckctV8a0Z5mFvV0aZu0 path=/acme/acme/new-order proto col=HTTP/2.0 referer=remote-address=":" request-id=1e2009f8822a "" time="2025-02-07T12:50:20+01:00" method=POST nameca_n once=MOBKXMSUUYV042QVhckctV8a0Z5mFvV0aZu0 path=/acme/acme/new-order proto col="https://localhost:443/acme/acme/certificate/fqyppG12d20PMTDT7Q0TFCAQLjvy VY" size=542 status=200 user-agent=golang.org/x/crypto/acme user-id= INFO[0051] certificate="MIICITCAI 6gAwIBAgIRAMVke/gKH10JyZkz89BwCgYIKoZIzj0eHk4QjEwM6GCSqGSIb3DQEBAQUAA4IBDwAwAQEAggEKA0I BAQDQg0117kN6N8Fz06IapRud0wP 74LAVWEG F4Zy9egK/Vh1sIR0uUayZNIrcFeg+1LSr/QqR9MOK4uP PER09JX In+AbK7V Zr69LxkF3L0x2eYNShbz6zpw98TK7sy0a6ZdrnoT9M60 p0qZaJj sBTEmy1z " duration=7.829µs 495s duration-n=27829645 fields.time="2025-02-07T12:50:33+01:00" issuer=Edge14 ss Intermediate CA" method=POST nameca_nonce=OUY42071F30HW7DT1L11U7E3Ia4 VV0uXh01 path=/acme/acme/certificate/fqyppG12d20PMTDT7Q0TFCAQLjvy protocol =HTTP/2.0 provisioner=acme public-key="RSA 2048" referer=remote-address=":" re quest_id=7062896e-b1d0-4058-b02c-028245547f8 serial="2076173228944373839585828 501478445937 size=1616 status=200 subject=user-agent=golang.org/x/crypto/acme i ser-id=valid-from="2025-02-07T11:49:20Z" valid-to="2025-02-08T11:50:20Z" </pre>

Figure 11: Flow of messages exchanged during ACME device-attest by the Client, Attestation and ACME CA

Figure 12: Example flow for signatures performed using the Public/Private Key pair generated during the attestation process.

database, the device-attest challenge is executed, and the node successfully obtains a custom certificate, with the private key securely stored in the TPM.

To verify that the certificate and private key were correctly generated and securely stored in the TPM, a data signing and verification test was carried out using the OpenSSL cryptographic library together with the TPM2-TSS provider, which enables secure access to the TPM's private key. This setup allows OpenSSL to perform signing operations directly through the TPM, ensuring that the private key never leaves the SE. For this procedure, the certificate must include the digital signature usage in its extensions. After generating a signature over a test message, the verification was performed using the public key contained in the issued certificate. The successful verification result, shown in Fig. 12, confirms that both the key and certificate were correctly generated and are operational. Consequently, they can be reliably used for other cryptographic operations such as establishing TLS connections or executing further digital signatures.

4. Threat Model for ACME device-attest with TPM

In this section, some of the potential threats that have been identified for the ACME protocol and for the device-attest challenge in particular will be explained.

- Replay attacks: the ACME protocol relies on exposing the ACME CAs to the network so that clients can find it and start the challenge. These exposed interfaces can be attacked by replay attacks, where an attacker repeatedly performs POST operations in an attempt to overload the server and prevent legitimate users from being served. To protect the ACME resources from these types of attacks, the requests have an anti-replay mechanism, where a nonce is given to each client and expected to be used when requests are made. Other solutions include adding a reverse proxy before the CAs, which can provide load balance between multiple CAs or protect against targeted attacks.
- Man-in-the-middle (MiTM) attacks: an attacker might be able to obtain information being transmitted by the ACME user to the CA (or vice-versa) and disrupt the process. For all the ACME challenges, there is a binding between the private key that the user uses to connect to the ACME Server, and the unique identifier over which the device needs to prove control over. This, and the fact that HTTPS is used for all communications, makes it very unlikely that the attacker can either snoop on the communication or try to finish the challenge themselves to obtain a key.
- DNS Tampering: an attacker that can modify the DNS records could point the validation results to an endpoint controlled by an attacker. For example, this could mean that the Attestation Statement from the Edge Node is redirected to another server that pretends to finish the challenge usurping the identity. Some mitigations for this include the use of DNSSEC to query the address, or querying multiple DNS providers to avoid DNS poisoning.
- DDoS attacks: since HTTPS is used to protect from MiTM attacks, this requires for some cryptographic operations that might be heavy for the server to be performed, specially if the flow of traffic is intense. Apart from this, there is the need to perform some other crypto operations and time constant comparisons in the CAs that also require resources. In order to limit the problematic of these types of attacks, rate limits can be applied. This includes limiting the rate at which new ACME accounts can be registered, limiting HTTP requests, or the rate at which new certificates can be issued to accounts, apart from the addition of a reverse proxy.

- Server-Side Request Forgery (SSRF): these attacks involve an attacker causing the ACME CA to perform an HTTP request to an URL they control. This way, they might be able to obtain information from the server such as debugging data, or force the CA to query an arbitrary URL. This is limited by forcing the CA to only communicate with servers in the public internet.
- TPM Key Compromise: if an attacker is capable of gaining privileged access to the device, they might be able to misuse TPM Keys. In this particular case, this might mean potentially signing fake data that might be sent to other vehicles in the VANET. Regarding physical attacks, they might also be able to snoop on the SPI line to try and replicate the private key outside of the TPM. Mitigations to these threats include limiting the access to the device, both physically and at the software level. On a software level, access to the TPM can be cut off to unprivileged processes, or only allowed under certain software/hardware conditions. On a hardware level, session keys can be used to provide encryption that protects data in transit between the TPM and the CPU.
- Nonce Reuse: If any of the nonces for the ACME session, to verify the device's identity against the Attestation CA, or the one used during the ACME challenge are reused, this might open the door to potential replay attacks. The best solution against this attack is marking nonces as used. Due to the requirement in the ACME specification of ≥ 128 bits of entropy, 2^{128} possible nonces are available.
- Unchecked certificates: both the Attestation CA and ACME CA verify the chain of certificates that the device and the TPM are providing, up to the Root CA that signed it. If there is an incorrect configuration and only intermediate certificates are checked, it might be possible that an attacker with trick the challenge. The validity of these intermediate certificates also needs to be verified.
- WebAuthn Format Spoofing: the WebAuthn object created during the challenge with the ACME CA accepts other formats apart from the expected of "tpm". The types of format that are allowed by the ACME CA can be controlled in its configuration, and if they are wanted by

the user but not available from the CA side, the behavior of the CA should be to return an error.

- **Unique Identifier Spoofing:** during the challenge, the device proves control over the permanent identifier, which is obtained from the TPM. If the permanent identifier is cloned, then it might be possible for an attacker to obtain a valid certificate. Since this permanent identifier is uniquely linked to the device and it is pre-commissioned in the Attestation CA and actively verified, it is not likely for an attacker to spoof this information and be able to complete the challenge, given that the necessary keys are unique and stored in that particular TPM.

5. Use in Vehicular Networks

5.1. Integration with current Vehicular PKI

The ACME protocol automates the process of obtaining, renewing, and managing digital certificates. In addition, it has been demonstrated that ACME device-attest-01 challenge also allows devices to prove their identity and integrity using SEs like a TPM during certificate enrollment. This is particularly interesting for V2V and V2I secure communication in VANET networks, as it directly addresses their core security requirements [35]:

1. **Authentication:** Ensures that vehicles are properly identified and authorized before participating in network communication.
2. **Authorization:** Allows vehicles to verify that the sender of a message possesses a valid and trusted identity.
3. **Confidentiality:** Guarantees that transmitted messages remain private and inaccessible to unauthorized entities.
4. **Integrity:** Ensures that received messages have not been altered or tampered with during transmission.
5. **Replay Protection:** Maintains message freshness to prevent replay attacks.
6. **Non-repudiation:** Prevents vehicles from denying the transmission of previously sent messages, ensuring accountability in the case of misuse or malicious activity.

The IEEE 1609.2 and ETSI TS 102 940 standards define the security services for V2V communication. Both are built upon a Vehicular Public

Key Infrastructure (VPKI), which provisions and manages digital credentials for vehicles. Therefore, in the model that we propose, each vehicle is also equipped with a unique public-private key pair and receives digital certificates from a trusted CA. As long as the private key remains secure, vehicles can authenticate one another, and the confidentiality and integrity of exchanged data can be ensured through encryption and digital signatures.

Focusing on ETSI TS 102 940, the high-level structure of the VPKI is illustrated in Fig. 13. At the top of the hierarchy is the Root Certificate Authority (RCA), which acts as the root of trust and issues certificates to both the Enrollment Authority (EA) and the Authorization Authority (AA). The EA is responsible for issuing long-term certificates to vehicles (V-UEs) during registration. These certificates serve as a proof of identity and are used for authenticating vehicles within the VPKI. In contrast, the AA provides short-term certificates, which are used to secure V2V communications. Each message sent by a V-UE includes a digital signature and the corresponding short-term certificate. This allows the receiver to verify the sender's authenticity and the integrity of the message. For cryptographic operations, Elliptic Curve Cryptography (ECC) is typically used due to its performance and size advantages over RSA, particularly in resource-constrained vehicular environments. To maintain the trustworthiness of the network, CRLs are distributed periodically. Upon receiving a message, the receiving vehicle checks whether the sender's certificate appears on the CRL to determine whether it has been revoked [36].

Regarding the integration of this specific approach, if a vehicle runs Automotive Grade Linux (AGL) and includes a TPM, the IMA module can be enabled as described in [37]. In this configuration, custom measurement policies can be defined to specify which system components should be monitored. For instance, subsystems managed by the Linux OS (such as lights, brakes, or the steering system) can be "measured" by IMA. The resulting hash values are then extended into the TPM's PCRs, providing cryptographic proof that these components have not been tampered with and are functioning as intended. If the measured values deviate from the factory-provisioned values stored in the Attestation CA, this may indicate a system modification. In such cases, an alert can be generated to notify the user or the vehicle's control system. The ACME device-attest challenge can be initiated by the V-UE on a configurable schedule—daily, at each startup, or according to other application-specific intervals. During this process, the vehicle interacts with the remote infrastructure, and upon successful completion of the chal-

lenge, a valid certificate is issued. The corresponding private key remains securely stored inside the TPM, ensuring that cryptographic operations can be performed without exposing sensitive key material.

Moreover, privacy is a critical concern in vehicular networks to prevent tracking of users' movements. In this sense, the ACME device-attest protocol also allows for issuing privacy-preserving certificates, which omit unique device identifiers in the CSR. This ensures that certificates cannot be linked back to a specific vehicle. In addition, enhanced security can be achieved by enforcing TPM policies that restrict the use of the private key to certain conditions—such as specific PCR value combinations. This means, for instance, that the private key can only be used for digital signatures if the system is in a known, verified state.

Looking at the high-level V2V and V2I architecture (Fig. 13), the ACME infrastructure can be adapted to be integrated seamlessly. The RCA, which acts as the trust anchor, could remain unchanged or be extended to support ACME-based automated certificate renewal for the AA and EA. The EA, responsible for issuing long-term certificates during registration, could be integrated into the car manufacturing process. This would allow vehicles to be enrolled with valid TPM-based credentials at the factory. As for the short-term certificates issued by the AA, these could be generated on-demand using the ACME device-attest challenge. A fresh key pair can be created to protect communications, ensuring both data integrity and user privacy [38, 39].

Figure 13: ETSI Security Architecture with the ACME and Attestation CAs

Moreover, the United Nations (UN) has recently released UN Regulation No. 155 (UN-R155), which establishes mandatory requirements for cybersecurity and the implementation of a Cybersecurity Management System (CSMS) for vehicles in member states. Its aim is to align automotive security standards at a global level. The regulation outlines a list of potential threats and corresponding mitigation strategies. Notably, many communication-related threats—such as spoofing or impersonation—can be effectively mitigated through the use of ACME, as the incorporation of a TPM significantly increases the difficulty of carrying out such attacks [40].

5.2. Practical Implementation

To evaluate the feasibility of integrating the proposed solution within an Automotive Grade Linux (AGL) environment, a custom image was built and tested. Since the AGL project is based on the Yocto framework, additional layers can be included during the build process to support specific hardware configurations and software libraries. In this way, a custom image was generated for the Raspberry Pi 4 target, with added support for IMA as well as support for the TPM2 software libraries, including the TPM2 Access Broker (TPM2-ABRMD), and the TPM2 CLI tools (TPM2-Tools). Support for these features was added through the meta-security Yocto layer

[41], while a custom layer was developed to enable communication with the hardware TPM (OPTIGA™ SLB9672) connected via SPI, configured using Linux Device Tree overlays. A minimal image without graphical components was selected to minimize build time. Once the image was flashed onto the SD card, TPM accessibility was verified in the Raspberry Pi. Subsequently, performance tests were conducted by measuring the execution time of each cryptographic operation requiring physical access to the TPM. Each operation was repeated one hundred times to calculate the mean and standard deviation of execution times. The results are summarized in Table 1, comparing the performance across different Raspberry Pi models, the AGL implementation, and a software-based TPM emulator running in a Raspberry Pi 5. The following TPM operations were analyzed:

1. Open TPM: Initializes access to the TPM over the selected interface. This is the first operation executed, as it establishes communication between the device and the TPM.
2. EK: Retrieves the Endorsement Key(s) stored in the TPM. The public portion of the EK certificate is sent to the Attestation and ACME CAs for authentication during the challenge.
3. Info: Returns information about the TPM, including its firmware version and manufacturer (this operation is purely informative and does not affect the attestation process).
4. NewAK: Creates a new Attestation Key endorsed by the Storage Root Key (SRK). The AK is non-exportable and used to sign the attestation data.
5. AK Marshal: Provides the public portion of the AK encoded in a format compatible with TPM2-TSS applications. This enables the AK to be reloaded or regenerated at a later time.
6. Attest Platform: computes the necessary information to attest the software status of the device. Specifically, it reads and quotes the SHA-256 PCR banks in the TPM, producing data that can be sent to an external verifier.
7. NewKey: Similar to the creation of an AK, this operation generates a new application key endorsed by a selected AK. This key is used to respond to the ACME CA challenge. The generated key can be RSA or ECC, with ECC preferred for automotive use due to its smaller size and higher performance. The generation of this application key takes less time compared to the generation of the AK, as this latter one requires

Operation	RPi 5 (ms)	RPi 4 (ms)	RPi 4 + AGL (ms)	SW TPM (ms)
Open TPM	2.3 ± 0.1	2.2 ± 0.2	2.3 ± 0.2	1.14 ± 0.1
EK	15.0 ± 0.6	11.3 ± 0.6	10.9 ± 0.1	92.3 ± 0.6
Info	13.3 ± 0.7	10.2 ± 0.5	9.7 ± 1.2	6.3 ± 0.1
NewAK	4371 ± 4793	3939 ± 3584	4674 ± 4752	51 ± 23
AK Marshal	0.04 ± 0.01	0.12 ± 0.08	0.1 ± 0.1	0.01 ± 0.01
Attest Platform	3442 ± 11	3145 ± 6	3151 ± 6	64.4 ± 0.4
NewKey (RSA)	716 ± 4	675 ± 4	673 ± 3	89 ± 24
NewKey (ECC)	637 ± 3	595 ± 4	594 ± 4	41 ± 2
Activate Credential	1042 ± 7	1010 ± 160	960 ± 2	48 ± 1

Table 1: Timing comparison for TPM operations in tested targets

internal certification from the EK and other integrity operations, as well as operations with large integers for RSA, while the new application key is simply derived from the AK.

8. Activate Credentials: Authenticates the device by decrypting a secret within the TPM. This process proves that the AK was generated by the same TPM that owns the corresponding EK.

As expected, the software TPM exhibited shorter execution times; however, it lacks the hardware-level key protection provided by a physical TPM. As shown in Table 1, there is little difference in the execution times of TPM operations across the different hardware configurations, with the Raspberry Pi 5 being slightly slower than the previous model. This could be attributed to the different SPI controller used, since all devices were running a clean installation of Raspberry Pi OS based on the Linux Kernel version 6.12.25. The operation that consistently required the most time was the generation of a new AK, followed by the Attest Platform function. This result is expected, as operations involving the generation or cryptographic processing of RSA asymmetric keys typically demand more computation time. Overall, the TPM-related operations take approximately 10 seconds to complete: 9.52 seconds on the Raspberry Pi 5, 8.71 seconds on the Raspberry Pi 4, and 9.40 seconds on the AGL-based Raspberry Pi. Note that this timing could be further reduced if the operations relying on asymmetric cryptography (i.e., EK, NewAK, Attest Platform, and Activate Credential as shown in Table 1) were executed using ECC keys instead of RSA keys. RSA operations, due to their larger key sizes and the underlying mathematical complexity associated with large integer factorization, require more time and computational resources than their ECC counterparts. Currently, the use of ECC-based Endorse-

Operation	ECC ESAPI Time (ms)	Time reduction (%)
NewAK	1044.74 \pm 10.72	418
Attest Platform	434.53 \pm 10.07	792
Activate Credential	349.26 \pm 7.04	298

Table 2: Timing for ECC Operations using equivalent TPM ESAPI

ment Keys for these operations is not yet supported in the Go library used for the attestation process on Linux, as this capability is only available in the Windows OS. To establish a new baseline for performance improvement, equivalent code was implemented using the same TPM and the Enhanced System API (ESAPI) to replicate the same operations. Only functions affected by the RSA-to-ECC transition were measured, i.e., operations such as Open TPM, EK, or Info, which are independent of the key type, were excluded. The experiment was repeated under identical conditions using the Raspberry Pi 5, obtaining the results shown in Table 2, where a significant reduction in processing time can be observed. The total TPM operation time decreased from approximately 10.25 seconds to 2.5 seconds, representing more than a 400% improvement. Fig. 14 illustrates the execution time for each individual operation.

To complement the TPM performance evaluation, an additional measurement was conducted to assess the communication overhead associated with the attestation and certificate issuance process. This analysis is critical in the context of vehicular or edge-based deployments, where network bandwidth and latency can significantly affect system responsiveness. By quantifying the amount of data exchanged between the Edge Node and the CAs, we can better understand the communication requirements and scalability of the proposed solution. The experiment consisted of measuring the size of the data packages transmitted between the Edge Node and the different CA endpoints throughout the complete attestation and certificate issuance workflow. Each measurement was repeated ten times to calculate the mean and standard deviation of the exchanged data sizes. The results are summarized in Fig. 15, where the bytes sent and received are grouped by the corresponding CA endpoint:

1. tpmData: the Attestation CA and the Edge Node exchange relevant TPM data and the AK through this endpoint.
2. acme-challenge: the endpoint where the Edge Node answers to the

Figure 14: Timing comparison for TPM operations in chosen targets: (a) Open TPM, (b) EK, (c) Info, (d)NewAK, (e)AK Marshall, (f)Attest Platform, (g) New Key (RSA), (h) New Key (ECC), (i) Activate Credentials.

ACME device-attest-01 challenge.

3. `getSignedCert`: once the Edge Node successfully completes the attestation challenge, it uses this endpoint to obtain the *aikCert* signed by the Attestation CA, which is later required for the ACME challenge.
4. `dbRegistration`: endpoint used by the Attestation Server to verify attestation data and register the information from the request into the database.
5. `order-finalize`: after successfully completing the ACME challenge, the Edge Node sends the CSR to this endpoint to finalize the order. The CSR must contain the same verified identifiers; otherwise, the request will fail.
6. `acme-certificate`: endpoint used by the Edge Node to retrieve the signed certificate following a successful challenge, authenticated via the JWS token.
7. `acme-new-order`: endpoint where the Edge Node submits a JSON object containing certificate-related parameters, such as validity period and identifiers, to request issuance from the CA.
8. `acme-authz`: endpoint through which the client retrieves the authorization object associated with its certificate order. This object contains the available challenges and the current status of the request (e.g., pending, valid, or invalid).
9. `acme-new-account`: endpoint where a new account is created with the ACME CA. The request includes contact information, terms of service acceptance, and an optional external account binding object.
10. `acme-directory`: this endpoint is used as a discovery endpoint, where the ACME client can recover information regarding all the available ACME endpoints and metadata, so that it knows where to redirect the information.
11. `challenge`: endpoint from the Attestation CA where the attestation challenge is performed by sending an encrypted secret and awaiting a valid TPM-based response.
12. `new-nonce`: endpoint used by the Edge Node to obtain an anti-replay nonce, which must be included in subsequent JWS messages to ensure message freshness and prevent replay attacks.

As demonstrated by the error bars in Fig. 15, there is minimal deviation between executions, since the size of the exchanged data and challenge

Figure 15: Bytes transmitted by the Edge Node to different Endpoints

messages is predetermined and remains constant. A slightly higher deviation is only observed during database registration, following successful challenge completion, as the session's unique identifier is dynamically generated from the device's dictionary, introducing minor variability. Note that all communications between the client and the CAs is performed using TLS, where the CA servers are verified to be valid by the client during execution. This means that an additional 6.5 KB of data per CA is exchanged before any of this endpoints is reached in order to perform the TLS handshake. Once the TLS session is established, each packet carries approximately 40 B of overhead, corresponding to the TLS header and the selected Message Authentication Code (MAC) that ensures data authentication and integrity. In total, 26219 Bytes are sent and 6740 Bytes are received during the execution of the ACME device-attest-01 challenge. From these values, the transmission time can be extrapolated for different network technologies, such as 5G and 6G, following the bandwidth parameters discussed in [42].

For this analysis, it is assumed that the device obtains a new certificate each time the vehicle is started; therefore, no on-the-move certificate renewal process is considered. Although the throughput of 5G networks decreases significantly as the number of connected User Equipments (UEs) increases, the total amount of data exchanged during the entire process is only about 40

KB. Even in high-density 5G scenarios, the transmission time remains negligible. With the upcoming 6G networks, these values are expected to decrease further or, alternatively, to maintain the same throughput while supporting a larger number of users. Fig. 16 illustrates the estimated transmission time as the number of users increases, and consequently, as the available throughput per user decreases. Due to the small data size involved, even under high VANET loads, the transmission delay remains below 10 ms, confirming the feasibility of the proposed attestation and certification process in real vehicular conditions.

Figure 16: Time needed for the exchange of information as Throughput decreases

5.3. Discussion

While various solutions have been proposed to provide authentication and signature schemes for VANETs, they often rely solely on software-based implementations. As a result, they lack the benefits of a strong Root of Trust such as the TPM, which enables both secure key storage and remote attestation. Through attestation, a high level of assurance regarding the authenticity and integrity of the vehicle can be achieved, ensuring that it has not been tampered with. This mechanism also enhances user safety and transparency, as drivers can be informed of any possible security breaches or manipulations before operating the vehicle. Moreover, the proposed approach is based on well-established cryptographic standards, reducing the likelihood of vulnerabilities that often appear in custom cryptographic implementations.

A significant number of existing works rely on blockchain-based authentication frameworks [43, 44, 45, 46, 47]. While blockchain provides strong guarantees of immutability and decentralization, it is often computationally expensive, slow, and may involve transaction costs (gas fees) depending on the implementation. Other proposals employ lightweight authentication mechanisms using ECC and key insulation [48], where partial data exchanges and digital signatures enable identity verification. However, as previously discussed, these methods lack hardware-based protection, and therefore cannot ensure the same level of trust and tamper resistance as a Secure Element like the TPM. Another promising family of solutions, Certificateless Aggregate Signature (CLAS) schemes [49], aims to reduce the overhead of traditional PKI. Nonetheless, they depend on a Key Generation Center (KGC), introducing a potential single point of failure that could undermine system reliability.

In contrast, our approach integrates TPM-based attestation and key management directly into the vehicle's Edge Node, offering both cryptographic strength and hardware-enforced trust. After successful authentication, the TPM's private key can be used to sign messages using standard algorithms such as RSA-PSS or ECDSA. The latter is particularly advantageous due to its compact signatures and lower computational cost. Experimentally, an ECDSA signature operation using the TPM's private key was measured at 40.9 ± 0.9 ms, considering only the signing process once the hash is available. This delay is acceptable for VANET use cases, though it may increase if the packet size exceeds 10 MB.

For networks requiring lower signing latency, a hybrid strategy can be employed. A derived certificate and key pair can be generated and securely stored in a Trusted Execution Environment (TEE) or an equivalent hardware enclave, enabling faster software-based signature generation while maintaining the TPM-backed chain of trust. On the verification side, the integrity of the certificate remains intact, as it continues to trace back to the TPM's root certificate authority.

6. Conclusion

In this paper, we have presented a TPM-based ACME device attestation challenge that enables the automated provisioning of certificates to devices capable of proving both their identity and platform integrity. We implemented all the necessary components, including the Attestation and ACME

CAs and the client-side logic to issue certificates bound to cryptographic keys securely stored within the TPM. To illustrate a practical application, we demonstrated the integration of this attestation-based certificate issuance mechanism in VANETs. Vehicles equipped with TPMs can leverage this approach to automatically obtain ephemeral certificates, thereby achieving strong cryptographic identity assurance and attestation-based integrity validation. Because the private key never leaves the TPM and certificates are issued only when the device is in a known-good state, the system provides robust protection against spoofing, impersonation, and software tampering. To validate the feasibility of this integration within vehicular environments, we deployed the TPM and its supporting libraries on AGL and performed measurements to quantify the performance overhead introduced. The experimental results confirm that the proposed attestation workflow introduces only minimal latency and bandwidth requirements, making it suitable for real-time vehicular applications. Overall, this work demonstrates that the ACME device-attest challenge can serve as a foundational building block for scalable, automated, and hardware-rooted certificate provisioning in intelligent transportation systems. By aligning with the security requirements of standards such as ETSI TS 102-940 and regulations like UN-R155, this approach contributes to the development of a more trustworthy and verifiable V2V and V2I communication ecosystem.

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